

Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction: A Confirmatory Study in the Banking Sector of Pakistan

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to identify TL `s effect on employees ` JS Cross-sectional research design was selected for the study. Study participants were 177 employees from forty-one (41) private banks of district Swat. The instrument used for the study were Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MQL) Form 6 developed by (Avolio & Bass, 1990), TL scale developed by Hartog, De Hoogh, and Kalshoven (2013) and JS scale developed by Spector (1994). A convenience sampling method was applied for data collection. Results of the study revealed a significant positive association between TL `s components (IM, IC, II, IS), and JS IM and IS were the best predictors of JS.

Key Words:

Job Satisfaction;
Transformational Leadership,
and Private Banking Sector

Introduction

Organizations of the contemporary world strive to enhance their employees` wellbeing. They spend a large sum of money to identify the factors affecting employees` wellbeing. They pay more attention to the respective area, because of the realization of the fact that human assets (capital) have direct relationship with service quality and productivity level which plays important role in business growth and prosperity. In words of Mohammad, Al-Zeaud, and Batayneh (2011), Human capital is considered as the main factor among other organizational factors which plays important role in organizational effectiveness besides getting a competitive edge on other organizations.

Human capital not only plays an important role in an organization`s growth and prosperity, but it also provides a base for its smooth functioning. For the smooth functioning of business, there is a need of satisfaction amongst the members of an organization. Because unsatisfied employee won`t be able to

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perform his/her job effectively. Emery and Barker (2007) quoted John Smith saying that customers cannot be served happily by unhappy employees. Happy and satisfied individuals' will be more profitable and productive for the firm (Saari & Judge, 2004) as compared to unsatisfied. JS creates a sense of positive attitudes in individuals, enhance their performance, improve their morale level, and strengthen the relationship among them (Bushra, Ahmad, & Naveed, 2011). Bushra et al. (2011) further suggest that individuals who feel satisfaction regarding their jobs will be more innovative and creative, and be able to introduce positive changes in the organization necessary for its growth and development.

Plenty of studies examined the relationship between JS and its' different indicators or antecedents keeping in mind the objective to increase employees' satisfaction level. For instance, Baker (2004) applied the integrative methodology to examine the relationship between JS and its' antecedents. These antecedents have its' foundation in task characteristics approach, social information or leadership factors approach, and dispositional approach. In light of finding, all three viewpoints were JS 's significant predictors. Numerous scholars used the concept of Person-Environment Fit (P-E fit) concerning job attitudes which also include JS. They found a positive association between job attitudes and Person-Environment fit (Christensen & Wright, 2011; Giauque, Resenterra, & Siggen, 2014; Kristof-Brown, Zimmerman, & Johnson, 2005; Silva, Hutcheson, & Wahl, 2010; Vogel & Feldman, 2009). Another school of thought considered rewards and incentives as predictors of JS (Gabriel & Nwaeke, 2015; Oni-Ojo, Salau, Dirisu, & Waribo, 2015; Rafiq, Javed, Khan, & Ahmed, 2012).

TL has remained an attractive concept to many researchers for decades. Among other leadership theories, TL theory got more attention in the literature (Antonakis, Avolio, & Sivasubramaniam, 2003). Transformational leadership gives more stress on strategic and developmental thinking and thus, increases the change process of the organization to happen more quickly (Khalid, Hanaysha, Mat, Sarassina, Rahman, & Zakaria, 2012). In this style of leadership, leaders are supposed to induce inspiration amongst subordinates that empower them to visualize beyond expectations and sacrifice their interests for the team and organizational objectives (Avolio & Bass, 1990; Dubrin, 2001; Jandaghi, Matin, & Farjami, 2008; Northouse, 2004). In other words, in this leadership style, the leader goes side by side with followers and provides them with proper direction and assistance. Furthermore, TL creates a consistent value system between followers and leaders, and thus facilitates the environment where they stimulate each other for organizational goals' achievement (Krishnan, 2005).

Although a considerable volume of studies is present on JS and TL relationship, uncertainty remains regarding their relationship. Literature has evidence about their relationship as positive or negative. For instance, Abouraia and Othman (2017); Hamidifar (2010); Hukpati (2009); Mahmoud (2008) found a positive association between JS and TL. Thamrin's (2012) study revealed the

negative association of TL to JS As there is the lack of consensus in the literature regarding TL 's effect on JS Therefore, the present study aims to explore this relationship in Pakistan 's private banking sector to enhance the present literature regarding the relationship of these two variables. Additionally, the suggestion will be made based on findings to enable private bank management in enhancing their employee's JS level.

Literature Review

JS

The phenomenon 'JS ' derived the attention of numerous scholars towards itself. JS shows the amount of satisfaction and pleasure regarding one's job (Katherine & Daniel, 2016). JS shows the difference between a worker inputs made in a job and the outcome received from it. When the outcome is productive the worker gets satisfaction and dissatisfaction when it is unproductive (Vishwakarma, Shukla, & Nougriaya, 2015).

JS has positive effects in terms of commitment, performance, absenteeism, and turnover intention. For instance, Fang, Chang, and Chen (2009) recommended JS consequences as it has a positive influence on worker performance and organizational commitment. Thirulogasundaram and Sahu (2014) found a direct impact of JS 's intrinsic sources on absenteeism. Vishwakarma et al. (2015) found a direct linkage between teachers' JS and absenteeism. Randhawa (2007) identified a significant inverse association between turnover intention and JS.

TL

Burns (1978) first originated the term TL and Avolio and Bass (1995) further developed it. TL comes into effect when the leader encourages subordinates for boosting up their perception, motivation, beliefs, and morals regarding the objectives of the organization (Burns, 1978). Transformational leaders concentrate on employees and increase their perceptual level besides acceptance of organizational aims and vision (Avolio & Bass, 1994). Among TL characteristics, an important one is giving positive feedback to followers besides inducing extra motivation in them for the attainment of the organizational goal (Mujkić, Šehić, Rahimić, & Jusić, 2014). Avolio and Bass (1995) suggested four components of TL which are: IS, IM, II, and IC.

- a) IM shows leaders' capabilities using which they offer an attractive vision that stimulates followers' actions for both collective as well as individual goals (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Here, leaders envisage the desired goal, induce confidence in subordinates, and enable them to attain that goal (Behling & McFillen, 1996).

- b) represents leaders' abilities based on which they gain respect, trust, and admiration from followers (Muenjohn & McMurray, 2017). In this dimension, leaders display commitment, pave ways for new possibilities on personal sacrifice, explain the importance of shared goals and objectives, and also install pride in subordinates.
- c) IS shows a situation where, leaders pursue opinions, ideas, and inputs from subordinates to bring innovation in the organization, and thus, it describes the leaders who appreciate creativity and innovation by challenging common views and beliefs of the group. Transformational leaders stimulate the intellectual level of subordinates through solving tough problems, critical thinking, and challenging primitive ways of solving critical problems (Avolio & Bass, 1990).
- d) IC refers to considering followers or team members individually concerning their needs. Here, the leader works as a coach or mentor and listen to subordinates with patience, and also provide them opportunities for learning, recognition, and growth. The transformational leader develops a proper relationship with followers and considers them equally and helps them to attain their goals (Avolio & Bass, 1990; Bernard M Bass, 1985).

Relationship between JS and TL

Previous studies conducted on JS and leadership styles relationship, majority of them revealed that TL functioning better than leadership's other styles (laissez faire and transactional) in enhancing employees' JS (Ho, Dinh, & Vu, 2016; Kelali & Narula, 2017; Loganathan, 2013; Mujkić et al., 2014). Comparing these three types of leadership, transactional leadership works on the principle of giving and take or reward and punishment, TL gives stress on collective goals and interests, while in laissez faire no actual exchange of relationship between followers and leader takes place and thus represent a passive leadership style (Kelali & Narula, 2017). Regarding transactional leadership, Rafferty and Griffin (2004) stated as it involves give and take the relationship between subordinates and the leader where subordinates receive prestige or wages for obeying a leader's order or instructions. In TL as opposed to transactional leadership, a leader inspires subordinates for performing more than expectations by modifying subordinates' beliefs, values, and attitudes as contrary to simply acquiring compliance (B. M. Bass, 1985; Yukl, 1999a, 1999b). TL has more influence on subordinates' innovation and performance as compared to transactional leadership (Boerner, Eisenbeiss, & Griesser, 2007), and it also helps in accepting organizational change (Bommer, Rubin, & Baldwin, 2004). Producing JS among subordinates depends on certain traits such as clarity and solidity of vision, a leader should have these traits and transformational leaders have these traits (Sergiovanni & Corbally, 1986; Smith & Peterson, 1988). Hence, TL works better in employees' JS as compare to other

leadership styles. Therefore, the current study takes into account TL as the best predictor of JS.

As leadership theory flourished with time, and the process of leadership theory's growth continues yet. The same situation also experienced by TL regarding its components. Addressing controversy about TL dimensions, Rafferty and Griffin (2004) stated as, even though TL has received much popularity in the present era, the methods applied in defining the sub-dimensions in the model have been objected. Scholars used a different number of components of TL about other variables. Carless, Wearing, and Mann (2000) suggested seven components of TL such as staff-development, empowerment, lateral thinking or innovative, supportive leadership, vision, charismatic leadership, and guide by examples. Some scholars considered TL as a whole variable without having components in relation to other variables (Riaz & Haider, 2010; Thamrin, 2012). A number of studies used II having two subcomponents such as behavioral and attributed. Multiple scholars have been considered II, IS, IC and IM as TL's components (Brown, 2008; Horn-Turpin, 2009).

Literature has different results regarding JS and II relationships. Khalid et al. (2012) reported an insignificant positive effect of II on JS. Khalid et al. (2012) study's result was inconsistent with prior study's result, where II had significant positive effects on JS (Mohammad et al., 2011). The majority of the studies conducted recently or in recent past showed consistent results with Mohammad et al. (2011) findings. For instance, Rahman, Munir, Ma'amor, and Malik (2012) found a significant positive association between II and JS in Malaysian college staff. Malik, Hassan, and Javed (2017) study's result revealed a positive and significant association between II and JS. The study demonstrated a positive effect of II on JS based on above findings, the first hypothesis of the study is proposed as

Hypothesis 1: II has a significant positive effect on employees' JS in private banks of Swat.

Literature has relatively consistent results regarding the effect of IS on JS. IS has a significant positive effect on employees' JS (Khalid et al., 2012). Rahman et al. (2012) study also identified a positive effect of IS on JS. Hussin and Wan Omar (2013) aimed to find academic staff's JS relationship with TL at University Utara (Malaysia) and revealed positive association between IS and JS. In Malik et al. (2017) study IS was positively related to JS. On these findings' basis study second hypothesis is proposed as

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant positive effect of IS on employees' JS in private banks of Swat.

Previous research found both positive and negative effects of IC on JS. Khalid et al. (2012) study disclosed a negative effect of IC on JS. Hussin and Wan Omar (2013) also found a negative relationship between IC and JS. Khalid et al. (2012) and Hussin and Wan Omar's (2013) studies results were inconsistent with other

scholars' findings (Hamidifar, 2010; Loganathan, 2013; Malik et al., 2017; Rahman et al., 2012). Inconsistency among the results, regarding the relationship between these two variables, may depend on service or sector type. A majority of studies has been reported a positive relationship between these two variables (Hamidifar, 2010; Loganathan, 2013; Malik et al., 2017; Rahman et al., 2012). Here, we expect a replication of the positive relationship between these two variables and propose our third hypothesis as

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant positive effect of IC on employees' job satisfaction in private banks of Swat.

Majority of previous studies reported that IM has a positive relationship with employees' JS Hukpati (2009) conducted comparative research of public and private tertiary institutions in Ghana and found a positive relationship between IM and JS Studies conducted in various sectors after Hukpati (2009), also demonstrated the same result (Malik et al., 2017; Rahman et al., 2012). Based on the consistency among previous studies' results, in the present study, we expect a replication of the previous results regarding the relationship of these two variables and propose

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant positive effect of IM on employees' job satisfaction in private banks of Swat.

This study will test the above-proposed hypotheses. Based on the results, the proposed hypotheses will be accepted or rejected. Furthermore, results will be compared with previous studies' results, and based on comparison suggestions will be made for the banking sector's management to increase their employees' satisfaction level.

Testing association between TL and JS, scholars examined the association between these two variables considering each variable as a whole i.e. TL and JS (Bushra et al., 2011; Chang, 2017; Mahmoud, 2008) as well as between JS and TL's components (Hamidifar, 2010; Mujkić et al., 2014). The present study is aimed at examining this association between JS and TL's components.

Methodology

Participants and Procedures

The present study's population was private banking employees of district Swat (Khyber Pakhtoonkhwa, Pakistan). Participants were 177 employees (98.3% male and 1.7% female) from 41 private banks of district Swat (Khyber Pakhtoonkhwa). The age of the respondents ranged from 25 to 59 with a mean (average) score of 40.94 and a Standard deviation of 7.91. Their educational level ranged from Bachelor to MS/MPhil. Forty-three (43) percent of the participants had Master/ BS (Hons), and 38.5 had MS/MPhil, and 18.6 percent had bachelor qualification. Their designation ranged from Cashier-Teller- Receptionist to Operation manager. 31.6

percent of the participants were Cashier-Teller- Receptionist, 19.2 percent were general banking managers, 16.9 percent were operation managers, 16.4 percent were operational officers, and 15.8 percent were relationship managers. They had job experience range from one (1) year to seventeen (17) years and above. Participants had 10.51 average experiences with a standard deviation of 2.56. Questionnaires among the participants were distributed personally by the researcher visiting the banks. A total of 190 questionnaires was distributed among participants and 177 were returned and all the returned questionnaires were valid. The response rate for the study was about ninety-three percent (93.15%).

Instruments

To ascertain participants' JS 's relationship with leader TL behaviors, the following validated questionnaires were administered.

MLQ Form 6 and TL Scale

Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) Form 6 developed by(Avolio & Bass, 1990)was used for collecting TL related data. There is total of twenty-one items on this scale. We selected only twelve items related to TL 's four dimensions namely, IM, IC, II, and IS. One item for TL 's dimension was additionally selected from the TL scale developed by Hartog et al. (2013). Scale's items were weighted from disagreeing very much = 1 to agree very much =6. Cronbach's alpha coefficient for TL 's scale was 0.88.

JS Scale

For assessing participants' JS level, Spector's (1994) JS scale was used. This scale evaluates JS in nine portions, for this study only five portions were selected namely, work's nature, promotion, coworkers, supervision, and pay. On this scale, some items were worded negatively. Before adding the score of these items, the points were reversed. Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the JS Survey in this study was 0.90.

Data Analysis

Both SPSS and AMOS software was used for data analysis purpose in the present study. The demographic information of the participants was analyzed in the first step of data analysis with the help of SPSS. To analyze demographic information percentage, average, and standard deviation were find out. After analyzing demographic information, data was analyzed through AMOS for model fit. For

model fit both goodness of fit indices and badness of fit indices like NFI, CFI, GFI, RMSEA, and SRMR were checked for significance. The examination of the indicators revealed that the default model fitted the data well. Confirmatory factor analysis was performed in SPSS for dimension reduction. Correlation between JS and TL's dimensions was checked for significance through the Pearson correlation method. Multiple regression method was used to see TL's dimensions effect on participants' JS.

Results

Measurement Model

Confirmatory factor analysis technique was adopted for analyzing study's measurement model. Results of the model revealed that it fitted the data well. For JS : χ^2 (160, N=177) = 222.488, $p < 0.010$; GFI = .891; CFI = .967; NFI = .894; RMSEA = .047; and SRMR = .037. For TL : χ^2 (98, N=177) = 126.184, $p < 0.050$; GFI = .919; CFI = .981; NFI = .920; RMSEA = .040; and SRMR = .035.

Figure 1: TL's Model Fit

In figure 1, II represents II; IM represents IM; IS represents IS, and IC represents IC.

Note: Estimates are standardized

Figure 2: JS's Model Fit

In figure 2, P represents Pay, PR represents Promotion, S represents Supervision, CO represents Co-workers, and N represents Nature of work.

Note: Estimates are standardized

Correlation of TL Dimensions to Total Satisfaction

Table 1. Correlation between JS and TL `s dimensions is given below in

Variable 1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
IM		1								
II		.719**	1							
IS										
IC			.584**	.653**	1					
Pay			.324**	.337**	.427**	.291**	1			
Promotion			.353**	.468**	.467**	.402**	.642**	1		
Supervision			.436**	.537**	.412**	.477**	.540**	.680**	1	
Coworkers			.296**	.377**	.468**	.466**	.574**	.726**	.671**	1
Nature of work							.3**	.712**	.735**	1
.656**	1									
JS			.429**	.510**	.518**	.490**	.791**	.883**	.853**	.852**
.874**	1									

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

There was a significant positive correlation among TL `s components. There was also a significant positive relationship between the five factors of JS Regarding the association between JS and TL `s components. There was a present significant positive correlation among TL s` dimensions (IC, IM, II, and IS) and JS II had a significant positive correlation with total satisfaction (r = .429, p< 0.01). Correlation of IM to JS was also significant with r = .510, p< 0.01. Correlation between JS and IS was also significant with r = .518, p<0.01. Regarding the association between JS and IC, these two variables had a significant correlation with r = .490, p<0.01.

Study` s Structural Model

Figure 3 shows study`s structural model. Structural model fitted the data well having chi-square (χ^2) value (179, N=177) = 224.116, p<0.050; GFI= .894; CFI = .978; NFI= .902; RMSEA= .038; and SRMR= .041. From structural model, correlation among TL dimensions` items can easily be explained. Correlation among TL `s components can also be explained easily. Relationship between JS and TL `s components can also be explained easily.

Figure 3: Study’s structural Model

Note: In structural model II represents, IS represents IS, IM represents IM, IC represents IC, JS represents JS, P represents Pay, PR represents Promotion, S represents supervision, CO represents Coworkers, and N represents Nature of work.

Regression Analysis of TL’s Dimensions on JS

Table 2 provides information about the regression analysis of TL’s dimensions on total satisfaction.

Table 2. Summary of Js` Multiple Regression Coefficients.

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.331E-17	.050		.000	1.000
IS	.434	.054	.518	8.005	.000
(Constant)	5.409E-17	.049		.000	1.000
IS	.270	.069	.322	3.903	.000
IM	.254	.070	.300	3.631	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Jobsatisfaction

Note: For Model 1 Adjusted R² = .264 (p<.000) and For Model 2 Adjusted R² = .312 (p<.000).

Table 3. Summary of Excluded Variables

Excluded Variables ^a					
Model	Beta In	t	Sig	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics
					Tolerance
II	.192 ^b	2.446	.015	.182	.658

IM	.300 ^b	3.631	.000	.265	.574
IC	.268 ^b	3.274	.001	.241	.591
II	.055 ^c	.598	.550	.045	.460
IC	.151 ^c	1.549	.123	.117	.409
a. Dependent Variable: JS					
b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), IS					
c. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), IS, IM					

Multiple regression (stepwise) method was applied to anticipate participants' JS based on TL's dimensions. In light of information present in Table 2, IM and IS were JS's predictors. II and IC were both excluded in the stepwise method process as their P values were not significant. For JS, regression equation is $F(2,176) = 40.864, p < .000$ with adjusted R^2 of .312. Participants predicted job satisfaction = $5.409 + .270 (IS) + .254 (IM)$. IS was best predictor of participants' JS with $\beta = .322, p < .000$ as compared to IM ($\beta = .300, p < .000$). An increase in units of IM and IS would bring an increase in followers' JS IC and II both were excluded in the stepwise process because of having an insignificant relationship with JS.

Discussion

The present study investigated the effect of TL's components on employees JS in private banks of Swat (Pakistan). All the proposed hypotheses were accepted in the present study. Discussing the first finding of the study, II had a significant positive effect on participants' JS.

Based on the study's results, here it is concluded that there is a strong effect of TL on employees' JS in the private banking sector of Swat. Particularly, TL's IS and IM components have strong effects on workers' JS Private Banks should equip their managers with TL behaviors. Managers of private banks should demonstrate such behaviors that motivate employees for collective goals attainment and induces confidence in them for achieving these goals. They should pursue follower's suggestions, ideas, and opinions and give them feedback in such a way that stimulates their intellectual level. Furthermore, give them such tasks for fulfillment which compels them for logical thinking and that will ultimately bring creativity and innovation in the organization.

The present study also had some limitations. First, the population targeted in this study was comprised of only private banks' employees of district Swat. Second, due to time limitation, a convenience sampling strategy was adopted for data collection, and data was collected only from 41 private banks of district Swat. The third cross-sectional research design was chosen for data collection where data is collected from all participants at the same time.

In the future, a comparative study should be of high value targeting both private as well as government sectors. Comparing these results will provide a better understanding of the phenomenon. Furthermore, data should be collected with a random sampling method from a large population for generalizing the results. Longitudinal research should be conducted in the future to identify the variations concerning time.

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